

HARMLESS

Final webinar: Major HARMLESS achievements

11th March 2025, 14:00 – 15:30h CEST, online

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 953183

HOUSEKEEPING RULES

Thank you for accepting these rules that shall ensure a smooth running of the workshop!

- Please use a **headset and mute your microphone** if you are not speaking.
- Please **deactivate your camera** if you are not talking.
- Please **raise your hand** if you want to say something or use the **chat function**.
- If you have a **question**, please use the **chat**. Start with typing “?”. Based on the entries in the chat the moderator will pick up questions for further discussion within the group.

Objectives

- Showcase HARMLESS key outcomes
- Special focus on the HARMLESS Safe and Sustainable Innovation Approach (SSIA) & our innovative Decision Support System (DSS)
- Pitch presentations of specific project results

Agenda

14:00 - 14:20

Overview of major HARMLESS results

by Otmar Schmid (HMGU)

14:20 - 14:40

HARMLESS Safe and Sustainable Innovation Approach (SSIA) / Decision Support System (DSS)

by Blanca Suarez (TEMASOL) and Susan Dekkers (TNO)

14:40 - 14:50

Q&A

by Otmar Schmid (HMGU)

14:50 - 15:00

Major HARMLESS achievements – highlight pitch presentations

2 min per pitch

• **New Approach Methodologies (NAMs)**

- High Throughput Screening (HTS) including omics (AOPs),
by Roland Grafström (KI)

- Proteomics – HARN-specific toxicity profile, by Veronica Dumit (BfR)

- Predictive modelling (in vitro – in vivo), by Agnieszka Gajewicz-Skretna (UG)

• **Ecotoxicity**, by Anders Baun (DTU), José María Navas and
Mona Connolly (INIA-CSIC)

• **Integration, analysis and visualization of data**, by Nina Jeliaskova (IDEA)

• **Early Warning System for regulatory preparedness**, by Andrea Haase (BfR)

15:00 - 15:25

Break-out rooms for pitch presentations

15:25 - 15:30

Outlook & future perspectives

by Otmar Schmid (HMGU)

Overview of HARMLESS major results

Otmar Schmid & Tobias Stöger

Helmholtz Munich (HMGU)

HARMLESS

- End: 30 April 2025 (4+ years)
- Consortium:
 - 20 Partners** from 12 countries
 - **2 Industries** (BASF, Nouryon)
 - **4 SMEs**
- www.harmless-project.eu

- 1 HMGU
- 2 BfR
- 3 KI
- 4 TNO
- 5 NRCWE NFA
- 6 BNN
- 7 IDEA
- 8 BASF
- 9 NOURYON
- 10 BAuA
- 11 SU
- 12 CEA
- 13 UG
- 14 INIA
- 15 DTU
- 16 TEMASOL
- 17 Misvik
- 18 NanoLUND
- 19 ERS
- 20 CIT

HARMLESS

Objective:

**Develop Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) Approach
for Advanced Materials (AdMa) in Product Development**

Overview - HARMLESS project

Data gap filling - NAM development
Focus on
inhalation exposure route and ecotox,
Establish **AOP/MoA-based grouping**
(multi-omics)

In vivo anchorage (animal experiments)
Dose-response, biodistribution, in vitro/in vivo
mapping; predictive toxicology

Safe and Sustainable Innovation Approach (SSIA)
for advanced materials

Stage-gated, user-friendly decision support systems (DSS)

Industry case studies

Databases, (big) data analysis
Multi-scale modelling approaches for functionality, safety and sustainability

Stakeholder engagement
Establish collaboration with national and international initiatives to achieve global impact

WP6 - Case Studies

- **Sector-specific approaches**, because industry sectors differ in *functionality and concern*, circularity, applicable regulation, intended use by professionals or by consumers, or in the environment.

CS 1 - Papermaking

Material: silica additives
Sector: manufacturing – accelerated dewatering

CS 2 - Paint formulations

Material: silica additives
Sector: construction – dirt repellent facades

CS 3 - Catalysts

Material: perovskites
Sector: automotive mobility – three-way-catalyst

La, Co, Ni, Pt, + Pd (~1%)

Focus of advanced case study materials

- **Mixtures of (rare earth) metals/oxides**
- **HARN (High Aspect Ratio Nanomaterials)**

SiO₂
HARN

CS 4 - Facade insulation

Material: aerogel fibre
Sector: construction – insulation

CS 5 - Agriculture

Material: modified imogolite multi-component nanotubes
Sector: agriculture – environmental plant protection

O, Si, C, Al, Mg, Zr, Cr, Fe, Co, S, Ca, Sn, Cu,* Au*
HARN

Inorganic nanotubes: Imogolites (Al, Si) (HARN)

Overview of the HARMLESS SSbD Approach

SSIA Approach

SSbD Decision Support System (DSS)

Early Warning System (EWS) within the Risk Governance Process for AdMa

1. Identification of **materials with concern(s) → Prioritization („Filter“ function)**
2. **Practical, modular and easy tool** for screening of AdMa (before or after market entry)
3. Aligned with HARMLESS SSbD facilitating the **dialogue between innovators & regulators**
4. Supported by an **online Decision Support System (DSS)**

Decision Support System

SSbD-Decision Support System (for innovators)

Early Warning System (for regulators)

Data and Model Generation

Data-rich environment - 37 NAMs in Lab / Pilot phase

Key Parameters

- External exposure
- Tissue dose and dose metric
– surface area (or mass)
- Shape/HARN
- Surface activity
- Release of toxic ions
- Inflammation, genotoxicity, cytotoxicity
- Ecotox (pristine, age/EoL materials)

Selection of related in chemico, in vitro, in silico NAMs

- *In silico exposure modelling*
- BET (or geometric surface area)
- In vitro and in silico dosimetry tools
- Electron Microscopy (geometry)
- In chemico ROS via FRAS, EPR, or DCFH
- *Cellular oxidative stress via protein carbonylation*
- In chemico solubility/transformation in relevant media
 - Phagolysosomal simulant fluid (human tox)
 - pH 7.4 aquatic media
- *In vitro (e.g. air-liquid interface & high-throughput)*
- *Benchmark dose & clustering-based grouping*
- *In silico: Predictive hazard modelling & read-across*
- Omics-driven Predictive Toxicogenomics Space (PTGS) modeling
- Simulated release of materials during use
 - Occupational exposure & simulated life-time release
 - *In vitro/in vivo ecotox*

Integrated Approach to Testing and Assessment (IATA)

- Which NAMs should be performed for a given Advanced Material (extended from GRACIOUS project)

In silico descriptors (NAM)

>1000 molecular descriptors
per material

Quantum Mechanics -
electronic properties

Electronic system

$$[\hat{T} + \hat{V}_{ee} + \hat{v}]\Psi(M) = E(M)\Psi(M)$$

where $M = N - 1, N, N + 1$ number of electrons, \hat{T} kinetic energy of electrons, \hat{V}_{ee} electron-electron repulsion, \hat{v} external potential (nucleus-electron attraction)

- ▶ Ground-state $\Psi(N)$ yields density $n(\mathbf{r})$
- ▶ Ionization energy $IP(N) = E(N - 1) - E(N)$
- ▶ Electron affinity $EA(N) = E(N) - E(N + 1)$
- ▶ Band gap $\Delta_\mu[n] = IP(N) - EA(N) = E(N + 1) + E(N - 1) - 2E(N)$

Band gap as the functional of ground state $n(\mathbf{r})$ density N -electron system (expanded in perturbative series with respect to e^2)

$$\Delta_\mu[n] = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} c_i[n] = \underbrace{\varepsilon_{N+1}[n] - \varepsilon_N[n]}_{c_0[n]} + \underbrace{\langle \phi_{N+1} | \hat{v}_x^{HF} - \hat{v}_x^{DFT} | \phi_{N+1} \rangle - \langle \phi_N | \hat{v}_x^{HF} - \hat{v}_x^{DFT} | \phi_N \rangle}_{c_1[n]} + \dots$$

where $\varepsilon_{N+1}[n]$ and $\varepsilon_N[n]$ are the **LUMO** and **HOMO** KS-eigenvalues derived from KS-DFT for the ground-state of N -electron system, respectively.

Ionization potential
Electron affinity
Energy band gap
Electronegativity
Chemical potential
Electrophilicity
....many more

ZnCuInS/ZnS-COOH-S
(2149 atoms!)

NAMs – High-throughput in vitro screening , hazard ranking and grouping of materials

High throughput transcriptomics

$0.5-3 \times 10^6$ /analysis
reduced feature set
(400-2500 genes)

High-throughput cell-based screening

~25000 /analysis

NAMs – High-throughput in vitro screening , hazard ranking and grouping of materials

High throughput transcriptomics

0.5-3 x10⁶ /analysis
reduced feature set (400-2500 genes)

4 human cell types: alveol./bronch. epithelium (A549, BEAS-2B), liver (HepG2), macr. (dTHP-1)

Merging of endpoint scores into an integrated Tox-score
Ranking the scores against standards

High-throughput cell-based screening

~25000 /analysis

Ca. 25,000 data points / material

Comparison of the modelling-driven rankings (72 materials)

Reference materials

Case study materials

Concept of Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP)

AOP describes series/network of biological events leading to a disease (fibrosis)

Adapted from Aop: 173 (Sabina Halappanavar, Monita Sharma, Silvia Solorio-Rodriguez, Andrey Boyadzhiev, Hakan Wallin, Ulla Vogel, Kristie Sullivan, Amy J. Clippinger)

AOP-based mechanism-aware toxicity assessment

Halappanavar et al., P&FT, 2020

AOP-aware grouping for read-across/predictive modeling

MoA analysis of **MinUSil5** assessed in lung A549 cells (PTGS LOEL at 100 micrograms/cm²)

Proteomics – Key Results

ADVANCED SCIENCE

Research Article | [Open Access](#) |

Meta-Analysis of Integrated Proteomic and Transcriptomic Data Discerns Structure–Activity Relationship of Carbon Materials with Different Morphologies

Verónica I. Dumit, Yuk-Chien Liu, Aileen Bahl, Pekka Kohonen, Roland C. Grafström, Penny Nymark, Christine Müller-Graf, Andrea Haase , Mario Pink

First published: 20 December 2023 | <https://doi.org/10.1002/advs.202306268> | Citations: 2

Pathogenic carbon nanotubes show a clear transcript-/proteomic “fingerprint”

SPRINGER NATURE Link

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[Home](#) > [Archives of Toxicology](#) > Article

Towards characterization of cell culture conditions for reliable proteomic analysis: in vitro studies on A549, differentiated THP-1, and NR8383 cell lines

Toxicogenomics and Omics Technologies | [Open access](#) | Published: 12 September 2024
Volume 98, pages 4021–4031, (2024) [Cite this article](#)

[Rico Ledwith](#), [Tobias Stobernack](#), [Antje Bergert](#), [Aileen Bahl](#), [Mario Pink](#), [Andrea Haase](#) & [Verónica I. Dumit](#)

Different in vitro cell culture settings affect protein levels. Harmonization is key!

small **methods**

Research Article | [Open Access](#) |

Advancing Nanomaterial Toxicology Screening Through Efficient and Cost-Effective Quantitative Proteomics

Tobias Stobernack , Nils Dommershausen, Víctor Alcolea-Rodríguez, Rico Ledwith, Miguel A. Bañares, Andrea Haase, Mario Pink, Verónica I. Dumit

First published: 30 May 2024 | <https://doi.org/10.1002/smt.202400420>

Advanced proteomic protocol for toxicological screening.

Ecotoxicology - Proof-of-principle studies in a SSbD context

- **Persistency** evaluation = "does the material stay in the nano-range?"
 - Dissolution and agglomeration/dispersion stability
 - Dynamic system (Di Battista et al., 2023)
 - Static system (Hensel, 2023)
- The HARMLES **point-of-entry bioaccumulation** tiered testing approach:
 - Daphnia bioaccumulation studies
 - Algae-NM interaction studies
 - Confirmatory fish bioaccumulation studies
- The tiered testing approach is directly linked to the safety module in the HARMLESS SSbD approach

Fish cells and NAM tools

Rainbow trout (RT) gill epithelial cells: Rtgill W1
(*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) (Bols et al., 1994)

in vitro

TEST GUIDELINE NO. 249
Fish cell line acute toxicity:
the RTgill-W1 cell line assay

<http://oe.cd/testing-chemicals>

Lebowitz
L-15/ex medium

The RTgill-W1 cell line assay is intended as an *in vitro* alternative to traditional *in vivo* fish acute toxicity testing.

OECD 2021

3 in 1
High throughput
array assay

Alignment of ecotox – human tox: in vitro

EC50 – Cell viability (metabolic activity: Alamar blue (fish), CellTiterGlo (CTG) (human))

Nanomaterials

Types of cell lines

Nanomaterials	Fish Gill RTgill W1	Human			
		Lung epithelium	Liver	Macroph.	
		A549	Beas-2b	HEPG2	dTHP- 1
EC50 24h (cm²/cm²)					
LaCoNi	13	23		8	2
LaCoNi(5)	7	23	8		2
LaCoNi (16)	14	10		14	6
LaNi (22)	5	11		7	
LaCoNiPd	8	8		6	1
LaCoNiPt	9	23		10	3
CuO NM	1	34	35	10	
NRCWE-020 NiZnFe4O8	632		875		674
NRCWE-021 ZnFe2O4	21		122		184
NRCWE-022 NiFe2O4	284	271			764
Fe1CO1	353	488	144		312
FeCo oxides Fe3CO1	141	242	213		510
Fe1CO3	105	182			
Cobalt (II,III) oxide	17	13	22		

Perovskites

CS 3 - Catalysts

Material: perovskites

Sector: automotive mobility – three-way-catalyst

In vivo anchorage of NAMs

- **NAMs do not represent the entire complexity of animals and humans**
- **Animal models:**
 - Pulmonary application
 - Mouse
 - Rat
 - Ecotoxicity:
 - Rainbow trout

Predictive in vivo model - 72 HARMLESS materials

Doses: 1, 2, 6, 14, 18, 43, 54, 128, 162 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mouse}$
 Various time points: 1d, 3d, 7d, 28d, 90d

Descriptors:

- Dose
- Time of exposure
- Aspect ratio
- BET surface area
- Nanodimension
- ROS

Goodness of fit (training data)

Predictivity (validation data)

	R ²	RMSE _c	Q ² _{CV}	RMSE _{CV}	Q ² _{Ext}	RMSE _P	MAE	CCC
TDNA% BAL	0.84	2.15	0.69	3.01	0.91	1.51	1.28	0.95
TDNA% Liver	0.93	0.48	0.62	1.14	0.82	0.64	0.30	0.91
TDNA% Lung	0.75	1.18	0.47	1.71	0.77	1,03	0.69	0.87
Neutrophil influx	0.88	0.30	0.67	0.47	0.70	0,44	0.23	0.82

Types of predictive models

Types of predictive models:

- [Q]SARs: qualitative and quantitative models
- Local and global models
- Multiple modeling approaches:
 - linear and nonlinear regression;
 - decision tree classification and regression; Naïve Bayes, etc.

Most predictive descriptors:

- Phys/chem properties:
 - aspect ratio; BET surface area
 - ROS production, dissolution
- Electronic properties:
 - band gap energy, valance band; conduction band;
 - electronegativity

> 100 in silico HARMLESS models

eNanoMapper – much more than a “database”

- **FAIRification** – Creative Common Licenses
- High degree of attention to extensive characterization of material properties and assays (**SOPs, protocols**)

Make the raw/processed data FAIR by converting to a eNanoMapper data model and storing in NeXus format.

eNanoMapper – much more than a “database”

- FAIRification
- High degree of attention to extensive characterization of material properties and assays (SOPs, protocols)
- Data entry protocols - **Template Designer**

eNanoMapper – much more than a “database”

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- High degree of attention to extensive characterization of material properties and assays (SOPs, protocols)
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- Novel tools for **data visualization, processing**

eNanoMapper – much more than a “database”

- FAIRification
- High degree of attention to extensive characterization of material properties and assays (SOPs, protocols)
- Data entry protocols - Template Designer
- Novel tools for data visualization, processing,
- AI based *natural text data mining tool* (prototype)

The screenshot displays the HARMLESS eNanoMapper database interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Home, Project, Search, ADMA definitions, FAIR Tools Guide, and user information. The main heading is "H2020 HARMLESS - eNanoMapper database". Below this, there are several search and filter panels. A search box on the right contains the text "perovskites". The main content area shows a list of classes and subclasses, with "catalysis materials enabled by perovskites" selected. The details for this class are displayed on the right, including a definition, composition, functionality, properties, and applications. The interface also includes options to export data to CSV, PDF, or Print.

HARMLESS Home Project Search ADMA definitions FAIR Tools Guide [n10705013] Log out
Template Wizard Help

H2020 HARMLESS - eNanoMapper database

Class: catalysts (1), solar cells (2)

Subclass: catalysis materials enabled by perovskites (1), solar cells based on halide perovskites (1), solar cells based on perovskites (1)

Advanced: true (3)

Search: perovskites

Copy Excel CSV PDF Print

Class/Subclass Details

Definition: Catalysis materials enabled by perovskites are materials that use the unique properties of perovskite materials to catalyze chemical reactions. These materials are used in a variety of applications, including fuel cells, solar cells, and other energy-related technologies. Perovskites are a class of materials with a specific crystal structure that can be used to create materials with unique properties, such as high electrical conductivity, optical transparency, and catalytic activity.

Composition: Perovskites are a class of materials that are composed of a metal cation, such as titanium, and an anion, such as oxygen. These materials have been used in a variety of catalytic applications, including the production of hydrogen, the oxidation of organic compounds, and the production of carbon nanotubes. Additionally, perovskites have been used to catalyze the formation of metal-organic frameworks, which are used in a variety of applications, including drug delivery and energy storage.

Functionality: Perovskite materials can be used as catalysts to facilitate a variety of chemical reactions, including oxidation, reduction, and hydrolysis. They can also be used to promote the formation of new chemical bonds, such as in the synthesis of polymers. Perovskites can also be used to increase the efficiency of existing catalysts, such as those used in fuel cells and solar cells. Additionally, perovskites can be used to improve the selectivity of catalysts, allowing them

Properties: Perovskite materials can be used as catalysts to promote chemical reactions, such as the oxidation of organic molecules. They are also used in electrocatalysis, where they can be used to reduce the energy required for a reaction to occur. Perovskites also have high surface areas, which can increase the rate of reaction. Additionally, they are highly stable and can be used in a variety of conditions.

Applications: Perovskite materials have been used in a variety of catalytic applications, including fuel cells, water splitting, and the production of hydrogen. They have also been used in the production of ammonia, methanol, and other chemicals. Additionally, they have been used in the production of catalysts for the oxidation of organic compounds, as well as for the production of catalysts for the reduction of nitrogen oxides.

Definition: Solar cells based on halide perovskites are photovoltaic devices that use a thin film of a halide perovskite material to absorb light and convert it into electricity. These cells are highly efficient, lightweight, and cost-effective, making them an attractive alternative to traditional silicon-based solar cells.

Composition: Solar cells based on halide perovskites are composed of a thin film of a hybrid organic-inorganic material made up of a combination of lead, iodine, and organic molecules. The material is then sandwiched between two electrodes, typically made of a transparent conducting oxide such as indium tin oxide (ITO). When exposed to light, the material absorbs the photons and generates an electric current.

Functionality: Halide perovskite solar cells are a type of photovoltaic cell that uses a halide perovskite material as the active layer. These cells are highly efficient, with efficiencies of up to 22.1% reported. They are also relatively inexpensive to produce, making them a promising alternative to traditional silicon-based solar cells. Halide perovskite solar cells are able to absorb a wide range of wavelengths of light, allowing them to generate electricity from both direct and

Properties: Halide perovskite solar cells have several advantageous properties, including high efficiency, low cost, and low temperature processing. They also have a wide range of tunable optical and electrical properties, allowing for the optimization of device performance. Additionally, they are lightweight and flexible, making them suitable for a variety of applications.

Applications: Halide perovskite solar cells have a wide range of applications, including powering small electronic devices, powering homes and businesses, and providing energy for transportation. They can also be used in solar farms to generate large amounts of electricity. Additionally, halide perovskite solar cells can be used in space exploration, as they are lightweight and efficient.

Class/Subclass

catalysts

catalysis materials enabled by perovskites.

solar cells

solar cells based on halide perovskites

eNanoMapper – much more than a “database”

- FAIRification
- High degree of attention to extensive characterization of material properties and assays (SOPs, protocols)
- Data entry protocols - **Template Designer**
- Novel tools for data visualization, processing
- AI based *natural text* data mining tool (prototype)
- **Integration into DSS**

Summary

- **Important Contributions to Test Method Harmonization**
e.g.: protocols high throughput omics & FRAS
- **Important Contributions to IATAs & AOPs**
e.g. improved HARN IATA (based on work in EU GRACIOUS)
- **Largest Dataset on industrial relevant Advanced Materials** (total: 70+; HARN & mixtures with metox)
– **valuable for several follow-up studies and projects**
 - In vivo & AOP anchoring of results & Predictive in vitro-NAM/ in vivo modelling
- **Major Contributions to Safe-and Sustainable-Innovation Approach (SSIA)**
 - **modular HARMLESS SSbD**
(better suited for innovative materials with little data)
 - **improved Early Warning System**
(in particular: improved screening tier)
 - tested in four industrial relevant case studies
(each with a comprehensive & unique data set)
 - **facilitated by an easy-to-use
online Decision Support System (DSS)**

 Diamonds ³

TNO innovation
for life

<https://diamonds.tno.nl/projects>

HARMLESS

**HARMLESS Safe and Sustainable
Innovation Approach (SSIA) / Decision
Support System (DSS)**

**Blanca Suarez (Temas Solutions (TEMASOL)) and Susan
Dekkers (TNO)**

HARMLESS

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